

Ancient Boeotians

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The Ancient Boeotians refer to the inhabitants of Boeotia, a regional ethnic group located in central, between Attica and Phocis. In the Homeric 'Catalogue of Ships' the region was divided into two regions, one called Boeotia and the other referred to as Minyan. The people of the region fit into the definition of Greek identity. The main deity of the Boeotians was Athena Itonia, who was worshipped at Coronea, as well as Zeus; the two became the chief deities of the region in the Hellenistic period. There were also a series of related cults to Apollo across the region, located at Mount Ptoion (this is also where epigraphic evidence shows the first mentions of the group's name), the Ismenion in Thebes, Telphousa west of Haliartos, Mount Thourion near Chaeronea, Tegyra near Orchomenos, and the sanctuary of Trophonius, who is some times a son of Apollo in ancient genealogies (Schachter [1967]). The temple of Poseidon at Onchestos was also a significant temple within the region, with shared use between the Minyans and Boeotians.

Date Range: 600 BCE - 400 CE

Region: Ancient Boeotia

Region tags: Greece

Ancient Boeotia

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Schachter, Albert. 1986-1994. Cults of Boeotia Volume 1-3. Bulletin for the Institute of Classical Studies Supplements.
- Source 2: Grigsby, Paul. 2017. Boiotian Games: Festivals, Agones, and the Development of Boiotian Identity. PhD Dissertation: University of Warwick
- Source 3: Mackil, Emily. 2013. Creating a Common Polity: Religion, Economy, and Politics in the Making of the Greek Koinon. Hellenistic culture and society. London and Los Angeles: University of California Press

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://oxfordre.com/classics/display/10.1093/acrefore/9780199381135.001.0001/acrefore-9780199381135-e-1123?rskey=GHoCbq&result=13>
- Source 1 Description: Entry about Boeotian cults in Oxford Classical Dictionary by Albert Schachter from 2015

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://inscriptions.packhum.org/>

– Source 1 Description: Packhum online catalogue of Greek inscriptions, including inscriptions dealing with ancient Boeotia

– Source 2 URL: <http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/>

– Source 2 Description: Perseus online ancient sources in both Greek and Latin, some of which deals with ancient Boeotia

– Source 3 URL: <https://topostext.org>

– Source 3 Description: Topostext online research tool for ancient history, contains ancient sources, maps, and information about individuals. - including information relating to Boeotian religion

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– I don't know

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):
 - Yes
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife:
 - Yes
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):
 - No
- ↳ Humans:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other features of iconography:
 - Field doesn't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

- ↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
 - Optional (common)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.
Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– I don't know

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– I don't know

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: Some famous examples includes the Leuctra victory monument to celebrate the defeat of the Spartans at Lecutra, and the Lion of Chaeronea erected after the battle between the

Macedonians and the Athenians and Boeotians.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– Yes

Notes: The Greek king of the gods Zeus was present in Boeotia both as a chthonic and sky deity. Schachter (2015) refers to Zeus Laphystius as the ethnic god of the Minyans, who inhabited western Boeotia. Alongside Athena Itonia, Zeus Caraeus was the chief deities of the Hellenistic federation. Zeus was also present as Zeus Basileus within Boeotia.

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: As elsewhere in the Greek world, genealogies attaches prominent

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– No

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - I don't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - I don't know

- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - No

- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - I don't know
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - No
 - ↳ Only through monarch
 - No
 - ↳ Other form of communication with living:
 - No

- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: They can at least appear in peoples dreams, as the Leuctrides and their father Schedaus appeared in the dreams of Pelopidas before the Battle of Leuctra (Plutarch, Pelopidas, 20).

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Two local deities, Trophonius at Lebadea and Amphiaraus at Oropus, can be considered human spirits as they were mythical heroic characters before being deified. Both are deities that had been able to provide omens and oracular prophecies.

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: If we look to the Leuctrides, these spirits clearly remembered the crimes committed against them by the Spartans.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: When the Leuctrides appears in Pelopidas' dream they were crying, clearly showing a display of sadness.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: When Schedaus and his daughters, the Leuctrides, appeared in Pelopidas' dreams, Schedaus provided Pelopidas with the instructions to sacrifice as auburn hair virgin. This led them to sacrifice as auburn haired horse before the Battle of Leuctra.

↳ In trance possession:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination processes:
– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Nature deities such as personified mountains, river-gods, and nymphs within the region are often confined to the natural areas around them.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: Some nymphs have the gift of foresight.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - Yes
 - Notes: An excellent example being satyrs.
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Some families can be genealogically attached to gods, heroes, and other supernatural beings within the region.
- ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Whilst not always clear, there would have been a local hierarchy of gods, heroes, and other supernatural beings. Athena and Zeus were the chief deities of the region in the Hellenistic period.
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

↳ Food:

– No

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– I don't know

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Tiresias serves as an example of a Boeotian being punished by a deity. When he was in the Peloponnese on the sacred mountain Cyllene, he spotted two snakes mating. Tiresias hit the snakes with a stick, leading Hera to punish by turning him into a woman. Tiresias then spent seven years a woman, in this time he became a priestess of Hera and even had children. But after seven years Tiresias again came across mating snakes, and this time he either left them alone or trampled on them (Hyginus, *Fabulae*, 75); but as a consequence he was released from his sentence and became a man again. Another story of a punishment of Tiresias is the story of 'The Bathing of Pallas', in which Tiresias stumbles across Athena bathing, in turn she punished him by blinding him (Callimachus, *Hymn 5 The Bathing of Pallas*).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: The Battle of Leuctra is a good example, as the Spartans were destined to die where their ambassadors had sexually assaulted the Leuctrides according to the myth. Yet, there were multiple places called Leuctra and it is possible that the Spartans were unsure about which Leuctra they would be defeated at (Husøy, 2021, 80).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– No

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.
– Yes

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
– Yes

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
– Yes

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:
– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– I don't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Boeotia was through large periods covered in this entry unified in a confederal or federal entity, possibly already from the sixth century BCE. Yet, the region consisted of several strong sub-regional and city level identity groups, making it a complex region with multiple levels of political and ethnic identity. Even though the region was unified for long periods of time, there were also periods of significant unrest within the region.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: For example with the officials of the Boeotian Federation.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Field doesn't know

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– I don't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

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